

AN OPTIMAL POWER SCHEDULING A SMART HOME USING GREY WOLF OPTIMIZER (GWO)

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December 5, 2018

Abstract

In this paper, GWO is adapted for Power Scheduling Problem (PSP). PSP is addressed by scheduling home appliances to a certain time horizon to minimize the electricity bill and peak-to-average ratio (PAR) and increase the comfort level of users. The simulation results shows the GWO efficiency in obtaining optimal schedule by compare its results with genetic algorithm (GA) results, where GWO exhibits and yield better performance than GA using the same scenario.

1 INTRODUCTION

Smart Grid (SG) is the next generation of traditional power grid which improves the distribution system to overcome the weakness of the traditional power grid. In contrast, SG probably will face an issue related to the power demand inflation in the upcoming decades, where is expected that the power demand will increase 56% by 2040 due to the population growth [1]. Therefore, the electricity prices are rising due to increasing the demand for the fossil fuels which is known that its cost increasing day by day. This issue motivates both power supplier and their users to optimize their power generation and the overall power demand, respectively. Since reducing overall power demand presents several challenges to the users, one promising alternative approach to power optimization has been to focus by power supplier on

reducing its power usage at peak periods [2].

In order to balance the power demand throughout the day, the power supplier companies have introduced dynamic price schemes (i.e, prices of power varies dynamically over time throughout a day) in order to incentivize the users to reduce their power consumption during the peak period by scheduling the appliances operation time and shift the electricity consumption load to the lower peak periods in order to avoid the high electricity tariff and reduce the electricity bill. Balancing the power demand during a day can be reduce the ratio between the highest peak time of power consumption and the average consumption (Peak-to-average ratio(PAR)) [2] [3].

Several meta-heuristic optimization methods have been recently proposed for PSP. These algorithms are Ant Colony Optimization(ACO) [4], Genetic Algorithm(GA) [3] [4], Wind-Driven Optimization(WDO) [5], Bacterial Foraging Optimization Algorithm (BFOA) [6]. However, most of these methods suffering of imbalance between exploration and exploitation which results to not obtain the optimal solution in some cases

The main aim of this paper is to use a meta-heuristic optimization algorithm proposed by [7] called Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO) In order to schedule the power consumption and minimize its usage in the peak periods to reduce the electricity bill, PAR and improve the user comfort level.

2 PROPOSED WORK

In PSP, an efficient algorithm for power scheduling is required due to the complex nature of the problem where it has three main objectives including reduction of electricity bill and PAR and improves the user comfort level.

2.1 Objective Functions

The main objective in PSP is reducing the electricity bill which is formulated as follows:

$$Cost = \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{s \in S} p_s^t \times pc^t \quad (1)$$

Where P_s^t denote to the power consumed by appliance s at time t , pc^t is the electricity price at time t .

The second objective is reducing PAR which is formulated in equation (2).

$$PAR = \frac{(P_{max}^t)}{P_{avg}} \quad (2)$$

where P_{max}^t is the maximum power consumed throughout the time horizon and P_{avg} is the average power consumed during the whole time horizon.

Users usually prefers that the appliances can finish their tasks as soon as possible. Thus, lowering waiting time rate for the appliances operating time (WTA) parameter is considering in the scheduling of the electricity usage in order to reduce the appliances waiting time and improve user comfort level.

$$WTA_s = \frac{st_s - OTP_s}{OTPe_s - OTP_s - l_s} \quad (3)$$

where st_s denoted the starting time of the appliance s , OTP_s and $OTPe$ are the starting and ending the period of appliance s , l_s is the time required from appliance s to finish its work.

2.2 Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO)

The mechanism of GWO is inspired by the grey wolves lifestyle and their hunting mechanism which formulated in 2014 by Mirjalili [7]. Grey wolves have four levels of their social hierarchy including alpha (α), beta (β), delta (δ) and omega (ω). Alpha is on the top of the social hierarchy and is the leader of the grey wolf pack. Beta wolves play the main role in advising alpha wolf. Delta belongs to the level which placed between beta and omega wolves in the hierarchy. The last level of the hierarchy includes omega wolves.

In GWO, alpha wolf is considered as the fittest value of the objective function while beta and delta wolves are the second and third fitness values, respectively. The GWO starts by initializing a population and all PSP and GWO parameters, then will calculate the fitness values of the solutions. Alpha, beta, and delta assigned as the best, second best and third best fitness values, respectively. The next phase of GWO is updating the position of each wolf in the pack using the equations [4, 5, 6].

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{A} &= 2 \times \vec{a} \times \vec{r}_1 - \vec{a} \\ \vec{C} &= 2 \times \vec{r}_2 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{D}_\alpha &= |\vec{C}_1 \times \vec{X}_\alpha - \vec{X}| \\ \vec{D}_\beta &= |\vec{C}_2 \times \vec{X}_\beta - \vec{X}| \\ \vec{D}_\delta &= |\vec{C}_3 \times \vec{X}_\delta - \vec{X}| \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{X}_1 &= \vec{X}_\alpha - \vec{A}_1 \times \vec{D}_\alpha \\ \vec{X}_2 &= \vec{X}_\beta - \vec{A}_2 \times \vec{D}_\beta \\ \vec{X}_3 &= \vec{X}_\delta - \vec{A}_3 \times \vec{D}_\delta \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\vec{X}(t+1) = \frac{\vec{X}_1 + \vec{X}_2 + \vec{X}_3}{3}$$

where \vec{A} and \vec{C} are coefficient vectors, \vec{a} is linearly decreased from 2 to 0 over the course of iterations and \vec{r}_1 , \vec{r}_2 are random vectors in [0, 1], \vec{X} is the grey wolf position vector.

3 PRELIMINARY RESULTS

In this section, the simulation results are discussed to evaluate the efficiency and performance of the GWO algorithm by compare its results with GA.

For GWO, the parameters are a set of population with size 100, the max number of iteration is 200, the lower bound and upper bound are St_s and $OTPe_s - l_s$, respectively. Within GA, the same number of population size and iteration are used. However, its probability of Crossover and mutation are 0.9 and 0.02, respectively.

The home appliances and their time parameters used to evaluate the algorithms are shown in table 1, where 24-hours divided into 288 time slots (i.e. each time slot is 5 minutes) is considered as time horizon for the scheduling process, LOC is the operation cycle for the appliances. The price tariff is adopted from Commonwealth Edison Company for 7th of June 2016 [8].

Table 2 shows the comparison between GWO and GA. The results prove that the GWO algorithm outperforms GA in terms of electricity bill, PAR and user comfort level.

Table 2: Comparison between GWO and GA

Parameter	Unscheduled	GWO	GA
Electricity Bill	91.29	74.53	77.40
PAR	5.42	3.41	3.56
WTA	0.522	0.356	0.482

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Table 1: Time parameters and all possible operations of the appliances of the proposed method

NO.	Appliances	LOC	OTPs - OTPe	Power (kW/h)	NO.	Appliances	LOC	OTPs - OTPe	Power (kW/h)
1	Dishwasher	21	108 - 156	0.85	20	Dehumidifier	6	1 - 24	0.05
2	Dishwasher	21	168 - 216	0.85	21	Dehumidifier	6	24 - 48	0.05
3	Dishwasher	21	240 - 288	0.85	22	Dehumidifier	6	48 - 72	0.05
4	Air Conditioner	6	1 - 24	1	23	Dehumidifier	6	72 - 96	0.05
5	Air Conditioner	6	24 - 48	1	24	Dehumidifier	6	96 - 120	0.05
6	Air Conditioner	6	48 - 72	1	25	Dehumidifier	6	120 - 144	0.05
7	Air Conditioner	6	72 - 96	1	26	Dehumidifier	6	144 - 168	0.05
8	Air Conditioner	6	96 - 120	1	27	Dehumidifier	6	168 - 192	0.05
9	Air Conditioner	6	120 - 144	1	28	Dehumidifier	6	192 - 216	0.05
10	Air Conditioner	6	144 - 168	1	29	Dehumidifier	6	216 - 240	0.05
11	Air Conditioner	6	168 - 192	1	30	Dehumidifier	6	240 - 264	0.05
12	Air Conditioner	6	192 - 216	1	31	Dehumidifier	6	264 - 288	0.05
13	Air Conditioner	6	216 - 240	1	32	Electric Water Heater	14	60 - 84	4.5
14	Air Conditioner	6	240 - 264	1	33	Electric Water Heater	14	220 - 288	4.5
15	Air Conditioner	6	264 - 288	1	34	Microwaves	1	78 - 90	0.8
16	Washing Machine	11	12 - 60	0.38	35	Microwaves	1	156 - 168	0.8
17	Clothes Dryer	12	60 - 96	0.8	36	Microwaves	1	228 - 240	0.8
18	Coffee Maker	2	60 - 90	1.5	37	Electric Vehicle (1)	30	1 - 90	3
19	Coffee Maker	2	204 - 228	1.5	38	Electric Vehicle (2)	30	200 - 288	3